

DISEASES OBSERVED IN HUMANS AS A RESULT OF ENVIRONMENTAL DISTURBANCE

Firuz Ilxomovna Nazarova

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10644263>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st February 2024

Accepted: 05th February 2024

Published: 07th February 2024

KEYWORDS

water pollution, Earth pollution, solid waste, asthma, heart disease, chemical elements, disposal.

ABSTRACT

This scientific paper provides extensive information on the impact of environmental pollution on human health. Environmental pollution is present from the beginning of life, as a result of which waste is formed. Waste management and recycling is one of the important principles of combating environmental pollution and contributing to the improvement of human health under the condition of air, water, soil, waste and noise.

Environment pollution most of the beginning since available is come. However, in today's day and this is himself a serious problem has become, and humanity's survive to stay the threat throws. This is what we breathe bearing to air exposure makes, we consume that food and we drink that water, natural reach causing produces. Resources, plant and animal species not to be going to bethe global scale damage will deliver. Ecosystem and land biochemical processes with a threat it poses. In this sense, waste production, production and management, great importance has. The environment and its as a result human health effects study, an important role has. Human activity is very negative consequences take comeit is mainly air and water pollution. This is as a result of the surrounding environment, pollution, uncontrolled forest be cut out and their rural resources to earth cycle, the ozone layer is violationof global warming, our planet, climate changes, natural disasters, accumulation of various waste (this, including radioactive), certain a plant and havyonlar species loss out - comes. This man survive to stay serious risk in and today's the day we all losses from the world are living, that I argue can. Every day large amounts of waste production is out and the surrounding environment has been contaminated. And this human health on a very large effect shows and various different diseases come out to get you come. Short - term effects as a result of come out konjenital anomalies, asthma, breath to get ways to infections, stress, anxiety, head pain, general circulation, everything be so, eyes and a breath to get the system with associated diseases came out.

Long - term pollution health effects chronic with associated diseases breath you get, the heart, blood vessels diseases, cancer and brain, nerves, liver, lymph gematopoetik, lung and kidney diseases came out. In fact, waste activate the problem you solve to for the most proper solution is not the environment pollution problem the above as noted, illegal, wheels, plastics, textile or other industrial residues activate and toxic substances, remove send still a big concern poses. Water pollution pollutants are substances that water is the source of

industrial physical, biological and chemical conditions causing out of which case, the corresponding untreated case 'tog'ri directly or indirectly water flow by the outpouring as a result of they come. This type of contamination, mainly, chemical ingredients pre - processing without or accidentally fresh water flow to start, oil and chemical from the container to pour or leak out when you happen will. Water pollutants, substances, the presence of hepatitis, encephalitis, gastroenterit, diarrhea, vomiting, stomach pain , such as health negative effects display can; even reproductive problems , and neurological diseases. Earth pollution, as well as, soil pollution, the earth of dangerous and poisonous chemical substances with is contaminated. This type of contamination is mainly to human activities, industrial activities, rural household chemical substance and waste wrong in not making as a result of they come. Earth pollution most often occurring chemical compounds, petroleum hydrocarbons, each of, pesticides, lead, mercury and other heavy metal fruit. Above stated mentioned all the risks to human health, a number of negative effects , causing it to be out can. Their effects on the head in pain, eyes irritation feature and skin rash such as mild symptoms ranging, much more serious diseases, up changed is. An example as, in the soil qo'rg'oshinning high amount of young children brain development, damage caused can. Other hand, to mercury exposure to the body of injury and the risk of increase can; kidney and liver damage, the same including.

Chemical pollution to the source of as, we identify we can, rural agriculture, industry, waste not to make and activate, whereas air pollution is the main contribution of the transport and energy is. However, the opportunities available in the environment, with associated health to risk and accumulated benefits of the reduction of health to maintain the costs of reducing with associated environmental policy and productivity increase them out increasing costs increase is going to. Solid waste sources and the structural parts identify, help who will solid household waste type and the amount note, of solid waste not to make methods and improper waste effects , infectious diseases spreading to bring who comes to health to maintain to manage an important role having is. In so doing, the government and politicians, especially in environmental pollution control and reduction with associated organizations waste generated to be causes into account them to take ,then you need to pollution , the amount of reduced, but this will do to we waste proper management we need. This while the man from the environment to the effects we see to ensure the commitment it takes.

Population (consumers) organic waste know you should , used and waste breakdown and then fertilizer as used be can, also, this condition existing pollution level in reducing, waste generated being an important role plays , and around- the environment destruction against in the fight effective solutions, one is considered. Work out companies also have an important role to play also in mind to keep you need economy and in the same manner , minimizing the goods work out to encourage use then waste generated be known. In so doing, the materials re - work and re - recovery , the level of increase in money bet waste ensure to the level of a decrease to bring comes and as a result human health to improve the opportunity it gives. That is, the use of promote to the plastic re - work such as events. Every time also education not, but education is the need of the role plays work out directed, widely to the public and waste re - working sector to increase a need, because of it, for example, the development of help will.Goods production in and out of dangerous chemical substances compared to less dangerous alternativalardan use , you should. In so doing, work companies out of more responsibility they are taking and re - work, for responsibility, this land is also wide the public

more again to work to encourage a policy to work out you need. That is in addition to, and this transport is movement and energy sectors in the most dirty areas, the policy so be must, more re - renewable energy sources to use directed or less dirty energy sources and personal transport use , you should. This tadbirlar the environment, improve , and human health positive contribution will add.

References:

1. Шавкатов, Х., Негмаджанов, Б., Фаттаева, Ш., & Арзиева, Г. (2016). Повторный пролапс половых органов у женщин. Журнал вестник врача, 1(1), 60-64.
2. Shavkatovich, S. H., & Negmadjanov, B. B. (2020). Optimization Of Pelvic Prolaps Surgical Correction Using Its Own Tissues. The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research, 2(12), 15-19.
3. Boltaevich, N. B., Asliddinovna, Z. N., & Shavkatovich, S. K. (2023). Incidence Rates of Genital Prolapse in Women of Reproductive Age. American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149), 1(8), 184-187.
4. Негмаджанов, Б. Б., & Шавкатов, Х. Ш. (2022). ЖИНСИЙ АЪЗОЛАР ПРОЛАПСИ РЕЦИДИВИ ВА АСОРАТИНИ ХИРУРГИК ДАВОЛАШНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. Scientific progress, 3(1), 886-890.
5. Мухсинова, М. Х., Утепова, Г. Б., & Убайдуллаева, О. Х. (2023). КЛИНИКО-ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ МАЛЫХ АНОМАЛИЙ РАЗВИТИЯ СЕРДЦА У ДЕТЕЙ. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(2), 624-631.
6. Мухсинова, М. Х., & Убайдуллаева, О. Х. НОВЫЙ ДЕНЬ В МЕДИЦИНЕ. НОВЫЙ ДЕНЬ В МЕДИЦИНЕ Учредители: Бухарский государственный медицинский институт, ООО "Новый день в медицине", (3), 170-175.
7. МЕЛИКУЗИЕВ, О., & Тургун, Д. А. М. И. Н. О. В. (2022). СИСТЕМА ЭНДОГЕННЫХ АНТИМИКРОБНЫХ ПЕПТИДОВ У ДЕТЕЙ, БОЛЬНЫХ ПНЕВМОКОККОВОЙ ПНЕВМОНИЕЙ. Журнал " Медицина и инновации", (3), 405-415.
8. Миронов, С. П., Кожевников, О. В., Иванов, А. В., Гаврюшенко, Н. С., Затона, Д. Б., Кралина, С. Э., & Азимов, Ш. Т. (2010). Современная технология остеосинтеза проксимального отдела бедренной кости при реконструктивных операциях на тазобедренном суставе у детей. Вестник травматологии и ортопедии им. НН Приорова, (1), 54-59.
9. Турсунов, Б. С., Азимов, Ш. Т., & Махмудова, Х. Д. (2007). НЕКОТОРЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ПАРЕНТЕРАЛЬНОГО ПИТАНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С ГЛУБОКИМИ ОЖОГАМИ. Аллергология и иммунология, 8(1), 285-285.
10. Рахматов, К. Р. (2022). TRANSPEDICULAR STABILIZATION OF SPONDYLOLESTHESIS IN THE LUMBAR SPINE. УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ, 3(6).
11. Рахматов, К. Р. (2022). НОВЫЙ МЕТОД ЛЕЧЕНИЕ С БОЛЕВЫХ СИНДРОМОВ ПРИ ДЕГЕНЕРАТИВНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯХ ПОЯСНИЧНОГО ОТДЕЛА ПОЗВОНОЧНИКА. Scientific progress, 3(7), 4-9.
12. Каримов, Ш. А. (2007). Продуктивные и некоторые биологические особенности швицкой и черно-пестрой пород крупного рогатого скота в условиях фермерских хозяйств. Автореф. Дисс. Канд. с-х. наук. Ташкент, 21.
13. Allaberdievich, K. S., & Juraniyozovich, T. B. (2022). Physiological And Clinical Indicators Of Cattle. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 6(9), 4066-4069.

14. Karimov, S. A., & Shakhnoza, T. (2022). MORPHOLOGICAL COMPOSITION OF BULL MEAT. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(09), 74-78.
15. Sherali, K., & Choriyeвна, J. N. (2023). Golshteyn sigirlarning sut mahsuldorligiga tasir qiluvchi omillar. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 6(7), 7-11.
16. Максудова, Ф. Х., & Кариева, Ё. С. (2014). Изучение реологических параметров 5% геля диклофенака натрия. *Вестник фармации*, (4 (66)), 57-61.
17. Кариева, Ё. С., & Максудова, Ф. Х. (2017). Использование методов математического планирования для выбора оптимального состава комбинированной гелевой композиции. *Химико-фармацевтический журнал*, 51(5), 60-64.
18. Maksudova, F. K., & Karieva, E. S. (2014). The diclofenac sodium release kinetics examination from 3% gel" in vitro" experiments. *European journal of natural history*, (2), 23-25.
19. Khadjimetova, K. R., Karieva, E. S., & Maksudova, F. K. STUDY OF RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF DEXRANTHENOL GEL. *ФАРМАЦИЯ ИШИНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ*, 71.
20. Гаипова, Н. Н., Максудова, Ф. Х., & Кариева, Ё. С. ОЦЕНКА КАЧЕСТВА СУХОГО ЭКСТРАКТА ПРОТИВОВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ ЯЛЛИГЛАНИШГА ҚАРШИ ТАЪСИРГА ЭГА БЎЛГАН ҚУРУҚ ЭКСТРАКТИНИНГ СИФАТИНИ БАҲОЛАШ *Ташкентский фармацевтический институт. ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ФАРМАЦЕВТИК ХАБАРНОМАСИ*, 39.
21. Karieva, E. S., Sadikova, R. K., ogli Karimov, O. U., & Maksudova, F. K. (2022). Study of amino acid and elemental composition of dry extract of Samarkand immortelle. *Farmaciya (Pharmacy)*, 71(8), 40-47.
22. Maksudova, F., Usmonova, M., & Karimov, O. (2022). STUDY OF THE SHELF LIFE AND STORAGE CONDITIONS OF ADAPTOGEN-CAUSED CAPSULES. *Матеріали конференцій МЦНД*, (03.06. 2022; Луцьк, Україна), 314-316.
23. KARIEVA, E., GAIROVA, N., & MAKSUDOVA, F. (2020). The Utilization Of The Strategy Of Mathematical Planning Of The Experiment In The Selection Of Auxiliary Substances For A Gel Based On Dry Extract" *Fitoinflam"*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* (09752366), 12(4).
24. Каримов, Ш. А. (2007). Продуктивные и некоторые биологические особенности швицкой и черно-пестрой пород крупного рогатого скота в условиях фермерских хозяйств. Автореф. Дисс. Канд. с-х. наук. Ташкент, 21.
25. Sherali, K., & Choriyeвна, J. N. (2023). Golshteyn sigirlarning sut mahsuldorligiga tasir qiluvchi omillar. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 6(7), 7-11.
26. Allaberdievich, K. S., & Juraniyozovich, T. B. (2022). Physiological And Clinical Indicators Of Cattle. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(9), 4066-4069.
27. Kidirbergenovich, N. T., & Kaharov, A. (2020). Morphological structure of the meat of bull-calves in different genotype in the condition of Karakalpakstan. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 9(2), 125-131.